

A TWO-PLY TERMINATION STRATEGY FOR MECHANICALLY COUPLED TAPERED LAMINATES

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Keywords: Laminate Taper, Extension-Shearing Coupling, Bending-Twisting Coupling, Laminate Design Heuristics, Warp Free Designs.

ABSTRACT

A two-ply termination algorithm is employed to develop permissible tapered designs, with ply contiguity constraints, in which consistent mechanical coupling characteristics and immunity to thermal warping distortion are preserved. The tapered designs are representative of laminates with fully uncoupled properties, as well as those possessing *Extension-Shearing* and/or *Bending-Twisting* coupling. The results presented represent typical fuselage skin thicknesses, i.e., with between ($n =$) 12 and 16 plies, but consideration is also given to new fuselage design concepts with geodesic stiffener arrangements, for which thinner designs ($n \geq 8$) are also of interest. Consideration is given to the potential effectiveness of introducing tailored mechanical coupling through ply terminations, e.g. to induce bending-twisting coupling in parts of a structure, through increasing laminate level *Extension-Shearing* coupling, whilst maintaining fully uncoupled behaviour elsewhere in the structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

A recent study on single-ply terminations [1] investigated the extent of the design space for tapered laminates when the ubiquitous balanced and/or symmetric design rules are relaxed. Consideration of design heuristics, involving ply contiguity (≤ 2), representing the most severe design constraints for tapered laminates, were found to significantly influence the form of the designs, i.e., single ply terminations are possible only at the laminate mid-plane for consistent mechanically (de-)coupled characteristics. Nevertheless, this constraint may be desirable for mitigation of load path fluctuations and in-plane loading eccentricities. Several key observations were also made from the results presented: Tapered laminate solutions arise in non-symmetric, as well as symmetric laminates, with consistent mechanical behaviour and immunity to thermal warping throughout, for *Simple* laminate configurations as well as those with *Extension-Shearing* and/or *Bending-Twisting* coupling; Single cross-ply terminations are permissible in *Simple* or *Bending-Twisting* coupled laminates, but only within a mid-plane ply block, which can be non-symmetric; Single angle-ply terminations are permissible only in laminate configurations possessing *Extension-Shearing Bending-Twisting* coupling and; Consistent mechanical *Extension-Shearing Bending-Twisting* coupling can be preserved by modifying a mid-plane symmetric ply block, within an otherwise non-symmetric laminate configuration, which is applicable to both single angle-ply and/or cross-ply terminations. Most significantly, lamination parameter point clouds were found to reveal clear strings of points representing the tapered designs found, and demonstrating the potential for tailoring of stiffness properties through ply termination.

Similar tailoring strategies to those described above are now applied to unconventional tapered laminate designs (i.e. those free from the ubiquitous symmetric and balanced, or un-balanced, design constraint) with two-ply terminations. The extent to which angle-ply layers can be terminated without introducing *Extension-Shearing* coupling is investigated. Additionally, the extent to which angle- and cross-ply combinations can be terminated to tailor or maintain *Extension-Shearing* throughout the tapered laminate is explored. Consideration is also given to the potential effectiveness of changing the mechanical coupling properties through ply terminations, e.g. to induce bending-twisting coupling in

monocoque or semi-monocoque structures, using laminate level *Extension-Shearing* coupling, whilst maintaining fully uncoupled laminate behaviour elsewhere in the structure. This mechanism has specific application in: fuselage designs with helical stiffener configurations, to eliminate bending induced twisting, and; wing-tip or winglet designs, to reduce drag in aft-swept wings, or eliminate divergence in forward-swept wings.

With very few exceptions, tapered designs in aircraft construction are currently certified only for balanced and symmetric laminates [2], despite the severe design constraint that 1 angle-ply termination requires a further 3 angle-ply terminations: 2 terminations to maintain balanced angle-ply, and a further 2 to maintain symmetry. Balanced stacking sequences guarantee that *Extension-Shearing* coupling is eliminated by using matching pairs of angle-ply layers [3]. Symmetric laminates guarantee that coupling between in-plane and out-of-plane behaviour is eliminated, along with thermal warping distortions that would otherwise be expected. However, tapering of symmetric laminates with fewer than the requisite 4 angle-ply terminations is believed to be common in industrial practice [4], despite the fact that the effects on the structural integrity are not well understood; these effects are simply minimised by ensuring that terminations are made at the laminate mid-plane.

Recent research on laminate design has demonstrated that fully uncoupled laminates [5], or those with *Extension-Shearing* [3] and/or *Bending-Twisting* coupling [6,7] all have immunity to thermal warping distortion and, collectively, have a design space containing predominantly non-symmetric stacking sequences.

The results presented in this article are based on the four laminate classes, illustrated under free thermal contraction in Fig. 1. All are immune to thermal warping distortions by virtue of the fact that their coupling stiffness properties are null ($\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{0}$); as would be expected from symmetric laminate configurations. The first two classes contain balanced angle-ply layers, leading to uncoupled extensional stiffness properties. The *Simple* laminate in the first column is uncoupled in bending, whilst the laminate class in the second column possesses *Bending-Twisting* coupling. The final two laminate classes possess unbalanced angle-ply layers, leading to *Extension-Shearing* coupling properties. The laminate class in the third column is uncoupled in bending, whereas the laminate class in the fourth column has both *Extension-Shearing* *Bending-Twisting* coupling, as would arise from unbalanced and symmetric laminates. Note that laminates with *Extension-Shearing* coupling only were found to possess no tapered solutions within the ply number groupings investigated here [1,3] and are therefore not considered further.

Figure 1 – In-plane thermal contraction responses (exaggerated) resulting from a typical high temperature curing process. All examples shown are square, initially flat, composite laminates. The stacking sequences provided, in symbolic form, are representative of the minimum ply number grouping for each laminate class, with standard ply orientations ± 45 , 0 and 90° in place of symbols +, -, 0 and ●, respectively.

The remainder of this article is arranged as follows. Section 2 provides a summary of the derivation of definitive listings for the warp free laminate classes given in Fig. 1. A ply termination algorithm is described in Section 3, which is then applied to the definitive listings of laminates from each of the four laminate classes to develop tapered laminate designs and compatible stacking sequences for two-ply terminations; for computation expedience, the definitive listings are pre-filtered against ply contiguity constraints, i.e., the maximum number of adjacent plies with the same orientation. In Section 4, lamination parameter design spaces are presented visual interrogation of the tapered solutions. Finally, the potential for changing mechanical properties through ply terminations is discussed in Section 5, before conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

2 DERIVATION OF STACKING SEQUENCES

The common feature relating the laminate classes investigated here is that all are decoupled, i.e. $B_{ij} = 0$; hence in-plane and out-of-plane behaviour are independent and can therefore be treated separately. The constitutive relations simplify as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ \text{Sym.} & & A_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ \text{Sym.} & & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where non-dimensional parameters (n_+ , n_- , n_o , n_\bullet and ζ_+ , ζ_- , ζ_o , ζ_\bullet), derived elsewhere alongside the definitive listings of stacking sequences with *Simple* [5], *Extension-Shearing* [3] and/or *Bending-Twisting* coupling [6], facilitate the straight forward calculation of the elements of the extensional and bending stiffness matrices, using the transformed reduced stiffness, Q'_{ij} , for each ply orientation, θ , of constant ply thickness, t , from:

$$A_{ij} = \{n_+Q'_{ij+} + n_-Q'_{ij-} + n_oQ'_{ijO} + n_\bullet Q'_{ij\bullet}\}t$$

$$D_{ij} = \{\zeta_+Q'_{ij+} + \zeta_-Q'_{ij-} + \zeta_oQ'_{ijO} + \zeta_\bullet Q'_{ij\bullet}\}t^3/12 \quad (2)$$

The transformed reduced stiffnesses, Q'_{ij} , are defined by:

$$Q'_{11} = Q_{11}\cos^4\theta + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66})\cos^2\theta\sin^2\theta + Q_{22}\sin^4\theta$$

$$Q'_{12} = Q'_{21} = (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 4Q_{66})\cos^2\theta\sin^2\theta + Q_{12}(\cos^4\theta + \sin^4\theta)$$

$$Q'_{16} = Q'_{61} = \{(Q_{11} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\cos^2\theta + (Q_{12} - Q_{22} + 2Q_{66})\sin^2\theta\}\cos\theta\sin\theta$$

$$Q'_{22} = Q_{11}\sin^4\theta + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66})\cos^2\theta\sin^2\theta + Q_{22}\cos^4\theta$$

$$Q'_{26} = Q'_{62} = \{(Q_{11} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\sin^2\theta + (Q_{12} - Q_{22} + 2Q_{66})\cos^2\theta\}\cos\theta\sin\theta$$

$$Q'_{66} = (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\cos^2\theta\sin^2\theta + Q_{66}(\cos^4\theta + \sin^4\theta) \quad (3)$$

and the reduced stiffness terms, Q_{ij} , are calculated from the orthotropic material properties:

$$Q_{11} = E_1/(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})$$

$$Q_{12} = \nu_{12}E_2/(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})$$

$$Q_{22} = E_2/(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})$$

$$Q_{66} = G_{12} \quad (4)$$

Elements of the extensional and bending stiffness matrices can also be expressed in terms of lamination parameters, ξ_i , used later in this article, and laminate invariants, U_i , respectively, by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_{11} &= \{U_1 + \xi_1 U_2 + \xi_2 U_3\} \times H \\
 A_{12} = A_{21} &= \{-\xi_2 U_3 + U_4\} \times H \\
 A_{16} = A_{61} &= \{\xi_3 U_2/2 + \xi_4 U_3\} \times H \\
 A_{22} &= \{U_1 - \xi_1 U_2 + \xi_2 U_3\} \times H \\
 A_{26} = A_{62} &= \{\xi_3 U_2/2 - \xi_4 U_3\} \times H \\
 A_{66} &= \{-\xi_2 U_3 + U_5\} \times H
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{11} &= \{U_1 + \xi_9 U_2 + \xi_{10} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\
 D_{12} = D_{21} &= \{U_4 - \xi_{10} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\
 D_{16} = D_{61} &= \{\xi_{11} U_2/2 + \xi_{12} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\
 D_{22} &= \{U_1 - \xi_9 U_2 + \xi_{10} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\
 D_{26} = D_{62} &= \{\xi_{11} U_2/2 - \xi_{12} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\
 D_{66} &= \{-\xi_{10} U_3 + U_5\} \times H^3/12
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where the laminate thickness H ($=$ number of plies, n , \times constant ply thickness, t) and the laminate invariants, U_i , are calculated from the reduced stiffness terms, Q_{ij} , of Eq. (4):

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_1 &= \{3Q_{11} + 3Q_{22} + 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}\}/8 \\
 U_2 &= \{Q_{11} - Q_{22}\}/2 \\
 U_3 &= \{Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}\}/8 \\
 U_4 &= \{Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}\}/8 \\
 U_5 &= \{Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}\}/8
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

These ply orientation dependent lamination parameters are also related to the non-dimensional parameters by the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \xi_1 &= \{n_+ \cos(2\theta_+) + n_- \cos(2\theta_-) + n_o \cos(2\theta_o) + n_\bullet \cos(2\theta_\bullet)\}/n \\
 \xi_2 &= \{n_+ \cos(4\theta_+) + n_- \cos(4\theta_-) + n_o \cos(4\theta_o) + n_\bullet \cos(4\theta_\bullet)\}/n \\
 \xi_3 &= \{n_+ \sin(2\theta_+) + n_- \sin(2\theta_-) + n_o \sin(2\theta_o) + n_\bullet \sin(2\theta_\bullet)\}/n \\
 \xi_4 &= \{n_+ \sin(4\theta_+) + n_- \sin(4\theta_-) + n_o \sin(4\theta_o) + n_\bullet \sin(4\theta_\bullet)\}/n
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \xi_9 &= \{\zeta_+ \cos(2\theta_+) + \zeta_- \cos(2\theta_-) + \zeta_o \cos(2\theta_o) + \zeta_\bullet \cos(2\theta_\bullet)\}/n^3 \\
 \xi_{10} &= \{\zeta_+ \cos(4\theta_+) + \zeta_- \cos(4\theta_-) + \zeta_o \cos(4\theta_o) + \zeta_\bullet \cos(4\theta_\bullet)\}/n^3 \\
 \xi_{11} &= \{\zeta_+ \sin(2\theta_+) + \zeta_- \sin(2\theta_-) + \zeta_o \sin(2\theta_o) + \zeta_\bullet \sin(2\theta_\bullet)\}/n^3 \\
 \xi_{12} &= \{\zeta_+ \sin(4\theta_+) + \zeta_- \sin(4\theta_-) + \zeta_o \sin(4\theta_o) + \zeta_\bullet \sin(4\theta_\bullet)\}/n^3
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Noting that for standard ply orientations 0 , 90 and $\pm 45^\circ$, assumed here, $\xi_4 = \xi_{12} = 0$.

Lamination parameters permit an interrogation of the extent of resulting design space for tapered laminates, since individual laminate stacking sequences can now be represented by a single point in either a 2- or 3-dimensional space, representing either the extensional stiffness properties or the

bending stiffness properties. Each point, within the resulting point cloud, defines a co-ordinate set, from which the stiffness properties may be readily determined using Eq. (5) or Eq. (6).

In the derivation of the databases of stacking sequences [3, 5, 6], which assume (but are not restricted to) combinations of standard fibre angle orientations, i.e. 0, 90 and/or $\pm\theta^\circ$ ($= \pm 45^\circ$), the general rule of symmetry is relaxed. Neither cross plies nor angle plies are constrained to be symmetric about the laminate mid-plane. The derivations involved the added restrictions that each layer in the laminate: has identical orthotropic material properties; has identical thickness, t , and; differs only by its orientation.

For compatibility with the previously published data, similar symbols have been adopted for defining all stacking sequences, i.e., \bigcirc , \bullet , + and – are used in place of standard ply angle orientations 0, 90, +45 and –45°, respectively. Finally, to avoid the trivial solution of a stacking sequences with cross plies only, all sequences have an angle-ply (+) on one outer surface of the laminate. As a result, the other outer surface may be an angle-ply of equal (+) or opposite (–) orientation or a cross ply (\bigcirc), which may be either 0 or 90°.

3. LAMINATE TAPERING ALGORITHM AND RESULTS

The tapering algorithm involves: a two ply termination scheme, applied in turn to individual plies of every stacking sequence with n plies; comparison with all stacking sequences with $n-2$ plies and; recording exact matches. The results of the tapering process are presented in Table 1, for *Simple* laminates, noting that the first (or upper surface) ply is assumed to be continuous throughout the tapering process; this represents a practical design constraint to prevent surface ply delamination. This constraint is also applied to the last (or lower surface) ply, in practice, but has been relaxed in the results presented here; thus allowing for the possibility of lower surface ply terminations.

Table 1 – Results from the two ply termination algorithm applied to *Simple* laminates with even ply number groupings.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
16	260	164 (242)	442 (221/-)	44	218 (109/-)
14	74	46 (66)	122 (61/-)	22	154 (77/-)
12	22	10 (18)	24 (12/-)	10	24 (12/-)
10	4	4 (4)	4 (2/-)	4	4 (2/-)
8	1	- (1)	-	1	-

Column:

- (1) Ply number grouping, n .
- (2) Number of stacking sequences with ply contiguity ≤ 2 .
- (3) Number of n ply laminates from (2) matching $n-2$ ply laminates after top-down termination scheme. Number of n ply laminates matching $n+2$ ply laminates are shown in parentheses.
- (4) Number of tapered solutions between adjacent ply number groupings (n) and orientation (\bigcirc or \bullet /+ & –) of corresponding ply terminations.
- (5) Number of n ply laminates from (3) matching $n+2$ ply laminates after continuous bottom-up termination scheme. Number of n ply laminates matching $n-2$ ply laminates are shown in parentheses.
- (6) Number of tapered solutions arising from (5) within each ply number grouping (n) and orientation (\bigcirc or \bullet /+ & –) of corresponding ply terminations, for continuous tapering between 8-16 plies.

Column (1) contains the ply number grouping, n , ranging from 8 – 16 plies. Column (2) presents the number of stacking sequences with ply contiguity ≤ 2 , for *Simple* laminates [1]. Column (3) gives the results of the two ply termination scheme, which represent the total number of stacking sequences with

n plies, for which a matching stacking sequence is identified with $n-2$ plies. Matching sequences with $n+2$ ply laminates are presented in parentheses. Hence the first number in column (3) indicates that for laminates with 16 plies ($n = 16$), there are 164 of the 260 stacking sequences, which match 66 of the 74 stacking sequences with 14 plies ($n-2$). The first number in parentheses in column (3) indicates that 242 stacking sequences with 16 plies ($n = 16$) match stacking sequences with 18 plies ($n+2$), not shown. Repeated sequences are removed from the data presented in column (3), i.e., where multiple matches arise from different ply terminations within a single stacking sequence. The final ply number grouping ($n = 10$) to which this termination scheme is applied leaves a single match with ($n-2 =$) 8 plies. This forms a starting point for the second stage of the tapering algorithm.

The second stage of the tapering algorithm can be described as a bottom up process, and begins with compatible stacking sequences representing the minimum ply number grouping of interest. These sequences are then algorithmically filtered through higher ply number groupings, in turn, but now only sequences compatible with the minimum ply number grouping are retained. Once again, the two ply termination scheme involves the removal of individual plies, in turn, for each stacking sequence with $n+2$ plies, but now using only the column (3) results in parentheses, with a comparison made against each stacking sequence with n plies, and matches recorded. This procedure ensures that all solutions reported here will be compatible with higher ply number groupings beyond those given, i.e., $n > 16$. Hence, beginning with the single 8-ply solutions given at the bottom of column (3), which corresponds to the stacking sequence: $[+/-/-+/-/+/-]_T$, and applying the termination scheme to the solutions in parentheses for ($n+2 =$) 10 plies, the 4 matches found are reported in column (4), together with an indication of which plies are terminated, i.e. 2 cross ply pairs, corresponding to either \bigcirc or \bullet orientations. Note that termination of balanced angle ply pairs, + & -, necessary to maintain the uncoupled extension properties, were not found in even ply number groupings for this laminate class, which explains why the second value within parentheses is missing throughout column (4); signifying that only \bigcirc or \bullet cross plies may be terminated. The four matching 10-ply solutions are retained for comparison with the results of the termination scheme applied now to the 18 ($n+2 =$) 12-ply stacking sequences reported in parentheses in column (3). This procedure is repeated up to the highest ply number grouping of interest. The tapering of laminates between 12 and 16 plies, representing typical fuselage thicknesses, requires only a different starting point in the second stage of the algorithm; the procedure is otherwise identical to that described above and is not therefore given here.

Table 2 – Results from the two ply termination algorithm applied to *Simple* laminates with odd ply number groupings.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
15	246	144 (236)	460 (179/72/30)	54	314 (123/56/12)
13	54	40 (54)	130 (51/16/12)	28	118 (47/16/8)
11	18	14 (18)	38 (15/4/4)	14	38 (15/4/4)
9	6	- (6)	-	6	-

Column:

- (1) Ply number grouping, n .
- (2) Number of stacking sequences with ply contiguity ≤ 2 .
- (3) Number of n ply laminates from (2) matching $n-2$ ply laminates after top-down termination scheme. Number of n ply laminates matching $n+2$ ply laminates are shown in parentheses.
- (4) Number of tapered solutions between adjacent ply number groupings (n) and orientation (\bigcirc or \bullet / \bigcirc & \bullet / $+$ & $-$) of corresponding ply terminations.
- (5) Number of n ply laminates from (3) matching $n+2$ ply laminates after continuous bottom-up termination scheme. Number of n ply laminates matching $n-2$ ply laminates are shown in parentheses.
- (6) Number of tapered solutions arising from (5) within each ply number grouping (n) and orientation (\bigcirc or \bullet / \bigcirc & \bullet / $+$ & $-$) of corresponding ply terminations, for continuous tapering between 9-15 plies.

Table 2 presents the same basic information as described above for Table 1, but now for odd ply *Simple* laminate with between ($n =$) 9 and 15 plies. The key difference between the results lies in the fact that ply terminations are now possible as pairs of cross plies with the same or different orientation, or as balanced angle ply pairs, i.e. two angle plies can be terminated without changing the fully uncoupled behaviour of this laminate class.

Tables 3 and 4 contain the ply termination results for *Bending-Twisting* coupled or *B-T* laminates, for even and odd ply number groupings, respectively. As was the case for the *Simple* laminate class, only matching pairs of cross ply terminations are possible for even ply groupings, whereas equal or opposite cross-ply pairs, or balanced angle-ply pairs may be terminated in laminates with odd ply number groupings. Note that balanced angle-ply terminations can only be achieved in tapered laminates with ply number groupings of ($n =$) 11 and above for *B-T* laminates. Terminating balanced angle ply pairs below this threshold would result in a change to the mechanical coupling properties. This explains why the results of column (6) indicate no angle ply terminations in the tapered designs from ($n =$) 9 – 15 plies. Columns (7) and (8) have therefore been added to demonstrate the presence of angle-ply terminations in the tapered designs from ($n =$) 11 – 15 plies.

Table 3 – Results from the two ply termination algorithm applied to *B-T* coupled laminates with even ply number groupings.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
16	5,927	3,572 (5,927)	11,742 (5,871/-)	1,002	7,060 (3,530/-)
14	980	812 (980)	2,244 (1,122/-)	354	1,474 (737/-)
12	203	142 (203)	426 (213/-)	116	386 (193/-)
10	42	38 (42)	98 (49/-)	38	98 (49/-)
8	12	- (12)	-	12	-

Column:

- (1) Ply number grouping, n .
- (2) Number of stacking sequences with ply contiguity ≤ 2 .
- (3) Number of n ply laminates from (2) matching $n-2$ ply laminates after top-down termination scheme. Number of n ply laminates matching $n+2$ ply laminates are shown in parentheses.
- (4) Number of tapered solutions between adjacent ply number groupings (n) and orientation (○ or ●/+ & -) of corresponding ply terminations.
- (5) Number of n ply laminates from (3) matching $n+2$ ply laminates after continuous bottom-up termination scheme. Number of n ply laminates matching $n-2$ ply laminates are shown in parentheses.
- (6) Number of tapered solutions arising from (5) within each ply number grouping (n) and orientation (○ or ●/+ & -) of corresponding ply terminations, for continuous tapering between 8-16 plies.

Tables 5 and 6 contain the ply termination results for *Extension-Shearing Bending-Twisting* coupled or *E-S;B-T* laminates for even and odd ply number groupings, respectively.

Table 5 highlights the increased flexibility in ply terminations due to removal of the constraint for balanced angle plies. Angle-ply terminations are permissible in even-ply and odd-ply in *Extension-Shearing Bending-Twisting* coupled laminate configurations.

Table 4 – Results from the two ply termination algorithm applied to *B-T* coupled laminates with odd ply number groupings.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
15	6054	3,462 (6,034)	9,896 (4,071/1,526/228)	954	4,970 (2,007/956/-)	1,914	7,644 (3,079/1,346/140)
13	878	578 (878)	1,564 (615/294/40)	318	1,232 (490/252/-)	578	1,564 (615/294/40)
11	148	96 (148)	272 (102/68/-)	96	272 (102/68/-)	148	-
9	28	- (28)	-	28	-	-	-

Column:

- (1) Ply number grouping, n .
- (2) Number of stacking sequences with ply contiguity ≤ 2 .
- (3) Number of n ply laminates from (2) matching $n-2$ ply laminates after top-down termination scheme. Number of n ply laminates matching $n+2$ ply laminates are shown in parentheses.
- (4) Number of tapered solutions between adjacent ply number groupings (n) and orientation (\bigcirc or \bullet/\bigcirc & $\bullet/+$ & $-$) of corresponding ply terminations.
- (5) Number of n ply laminates from (3) matching $n+2$ ply laminates after continuous bottom-up termination scheme. Number of n ply laminates matching $n-2$ ply laminates are shown in parentheses.
- (6) Number of tapered solutions arising from (5) within each ply number grouping (n) and orientation (\bigcirc or \bullet/\bigcirc & $\bullet/+$ & $-$) of corresponding ply terminations, for continuous tapering between 9-15 plies.
- (7)-(8) Repeat of procedure in (5)-(6) for tapering between 11-15 plies.

Table 5 – Results from the two ply termination algorithm applied to *E-S-B-T* coupled laminates with even ply number groupings.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
16	20,363	17,305 (20,363)	76,407 (22,034/18,285/14,054)	8,878	57,136 (16,237/13,993/10,669)
14	3,551	2,912 (3,551)	13,451 (3,896/3,257/2,402)	2,198	11,923 (3,433/2,955/2,102)
12	675	611 (675)	2,511 (746/613/406)	549	2,416 (711/602/392)
10	149	137 (149)	458 (138/114/68)	137	458 (138/114/68)
8	35	- (35)	-	35	-

Column:

- (1) Ply number grouping, n .
- (2) Number of stacking sequences with ply contiguity ≤ 2 .
- (3) Number of n ply laminates from (2) matching $n-2$ ply laminates after top-down termination scheme. Number of n ply laminates matching $n+2$ ply laminates are shown in parentheses.
- (4) Number of tapered solutions between adjacent ply number groupings (n) and orientation (\bigcirc or $\bullet/+/-$) of corresponding ply terminations.
- (5) Number of n ply laminates from (3) matching $n+2$ ply laminates after continuous bottom-up termination scheme. Number of n ply laminates matching $n-2$ ply laminates are shown in parentheses.
- (6) Number of tapered solutions arising from (5) within each ply number grouping (n) and orientation (\bigcirc or $\bullet/+/-$) of corresponding ply terminations, for continuous tapering between 8-16 plies.

Design flexibilities increase still further for odd-ply laminates, as seen in Table 6, whereby combinations of cross- and angle-ply terminations are also possible. These results also contain a special laminate subset discussed in an accompanying article [8], where terminations are constrained to adjacent ply pairings of $\bigcirc/+$ and/or $\bigcirc/-$, representing bi-angle Non-Crimp Fabric material configurations, which may be either flipped, rotated or both.

Only results for the top down termination process are reported in Table 6.

Table 6 – Results from the two ply termination algorithm applied to E-S-B-T coupled laminates with odd ply number groupings.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
13	6307	5,123 ()	26,303
			(4,919/4,831/3,861/1,447/1,029/1,154/1,667)
11	1088	892 (1088)	4,583
			(808/774/609/300/208/228/340)
9	197	-(197)	

Column:

- (1) Ply number grouping, n .
- (2) Number of stacking sequences with ply contiguity ≤ 2 .
- (3) Number of n ply laminates from (2) matching $n-2$ ply laminates after top-down termination scheme. Number of n ply laminates matching $n+2$ ply laminates are shown in parentheses.
- (4) Number of tapered solutions between each adjacent ply number grouping (n) and orientation (○ or ●/+/−/○ & + or ● & +/○ & − or ● & −/○ & ●/+ & −) of corresponding ply terminations.

4. LAMINATION PARAMETER DESIGN SPACE

Lamination parameter design spaces for B-T coupled laminates with even ply number groupings, $8 \leq n \leq 16$, are illustrated in Fig. 1. These are represented by a 2-dimensional space for the extensional stiffness and a 3-dimensional space for the bending stiffness, i.e. for extensional stiffness, by ξ_1 and ξ_2 , and bending stiffness, by ξ_9 , ξ_{10} and ξ_{11} . Similarly, odd ply number groupings, $9 \leq n \leq 15$, are illustrated in Fig. 2. This facilitates a three view orthographic projection of the 3-dimensional space.

Figure 1 – Lamination parameter design spaces for B-T coupled laminates, representing: (a)-(c) bending stiffness and; (d) extensional stiffness for laminates with $8 \leq n \leq 16$.

Figure 2 – Lamination parameter design spaces for *B-T* coupled laminates, representing: (a)-(c) bending stiffness and; (d) extensional stiffness for laminates with $9 \leq n \leq 15$.

The tapered sequences highlighted by the strings of lamination parameter points in Figs 1 and 2 are, respectively:

<p> $+/-/-/\bullet/\bullet/\circ/\bullet/+/+/\bullet/\circ/\bullet/\bullet/-/-/+$ $+/-/-/\bullet/\bullet/\circ/+/+/\circ/\bullet/\bullet/-/-/+$ $+/-/-/\bullet/\circ/+/+/\circ/\bullet/-/-/+$ $+/-/-/\bullet/+/+/\bullet/-/-/+$ $+/-/-/+/+/-/-/+$ </p>	<p> $+/+/-/-/\bullet/-/-/+$ $+/+/-/\circ/-/\bullet/-/\circ/-/+$ $+/+/\circ/-/\circ/-/\bullet/-/\circ/-/\circ/+$ $+/+/\circ/\bullet/-/\circ/-/\bullet/-/\circ/-/\bullet/\circ/+$ </p>
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5. TAILORING MECHANICAL COUPLING PROPERTIES THROUGH PLY TERMINATIONS.

Some of the earlier results in this article demonstrated that consistent mechanical properties could not be maintained below a certain ply number grouping. However, it may be possible to find tailored solutions which introduce desirable couplings as a result of the ply termination process. This final section therefore investigates the scope for tailoring, or more specifically, changing mechanical coupling behaviour through strategic ply terminations. This ply termination strategy has clear practical application, for example, where there is a requirement to induce bending-twisting coupling in a wing-tip or winglet, using *Extension-Shearing* coupling at the laminate level, but maintaining fully uncoupled laminate behaviour in the tapered skins elsewhere in the wing-box. The strategy may also be thought of as a cross fertilisation process; to identify gateways between laminates with *Simple* or *Bending-Twisting* coupling and those with *Extension-Shearing Bending-Twisting* coupling.

This termination strategy met with limited success when employing single ply terminations, although a small number of solutions were found between certain ply number groupings. For example, there were 2 *Simple* laminate stacking sequences that resulted in 2 *Bending-Twisting* coupled laminates following single ply terminations between $n = 15$ and $n = 14$. However, these gateways are likely to be too restrictive in design practice.

Table 7 contains results for the transitioning between 14 ply *Extension-Shearing Bending-Twisting* coupled properties and 12 ply *Simple*, or uncoupled properties, within a tapered laminate with ($n =$) 8 – 16 plies. The format of the Table is similar to Tables 1 - 6, but here Column (2a) contains *Simple* ($A_S B_0 D_S$) laminate data, from Column (2) of Table 1, and Column (2b) contains *Extension-Shearing Bending-Twisting* coupled laminate data, from Column (2) of Table 5. Column (3) gives the results after applying the top-down, two-ply termination algorithm. Hence, 63 of the 260 stacking sequences from Column (2a), with ($n =$) 16 plies, match 132 of the 980 stacking sequences from Column (2b), with ($n-2 =$) 14 plies; 14 of the 74 stacking sequences from Column (2a), with ($n =$) 14 plies, match 32 of the 203 stacking sequences from Column (2b), with ($n-2 =$) 12 plies; and so on. The number of tapered solutions and corresponding number of specific ply terminations are indicated in Column (4), for each ply number grouping.

There are no transitions between even-ply *Simple* laminates and *Extension-Shearing Bending-Twisting* coupled laminates below ($n = 10$) plies.

Table 7 – Results from the two ply termination algorithm applied to *Simple* ($A_S B_0 D_S$) laminates with even ply number groupings and transitioning to *Extension-Shearing Bending-Twisting* coupled ($A_F B_0 D_F$) laminates between 12 and 14 plies.

(1)	(2a)	(2b)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	
	$A_S B_0 D_S$	$A_F B_0 D_F$							
16	260	5,927	63 (608)	202 (-/72/130)			(8)	8 (4/-/-)	$A_S B_0 D_S$
14	74	980	14 (132)	50 (-/16/34)			(12) 4	36 (-/12/24)	
12	22	203	4 (32)	18 (-/2/16)	28 (32)	106 (39/2/26)	(24) 24	84 (35/2/12)	$A_F B_0 D_F$
10	4	42	0 (6)	-	6 (31)	16 (6/-/4)	(20) 20	38 (12/12/2)	
8	1	12	- (0)	-	- (10)	-	(10) 6	-	

Column:

- (1) Ply number grouping, n .
- (2a) Column (2) results from Table 1.
- (2b) Column (2) results from Table 5.
- (3) Number of n ply laminates from Table 1 matching $n-2$ ply laminates of Table 5 after top-down termination scheme. Number of n ply laminates matching $n+2$ ply laminates are shown in parentheses.
- (4) Number of tapered solutions between adjacent ply number groupings (n) and orientation (○ or ●/+/-) of corresponding ply terminations.
- (5) – (6) Repeat of (3) and (4) for Column (2b) results, beginning with result, in parentheses, from Column (3).
- (7) Number of n ply laminates from (3) and (5) matching $n+2$ ply laminates after continuous bottom-up termination scheme. Number of n ply laminates matching $n-2$ ply laminates are shown in parentheses.
- (8) Number of tapered solutions arising from (7) within each ply number grouping (n) and orientation (○ or ●/+/-) of corresponding ply terminations, for continuous tapering between 8-16 plies.

Columns (5) and (6) present the termination results below the transition point, now with consistent *Extension-Shearing Bending-Twisting* coupling down to ($n =$) 8 plies. Hence, applying the termination algorithm to the 32 compatible solutions of Column (3), with ($n =$) 12 plies, 28 stacking sequences match 31 of the 42 stacking sequences from Column (2b), with ($n-2 =$) 10 plies; 6 of the 42 stacking sequences from Column (2a), with ($n =$) 10 plies, match 10 of the 12 stacking sequences from Column (2b), with ($n-2 =$) 8 plies.

The bottom up termination scheme begins with the 8-ply results of Column (5). Column (7) demonstrates that only 6 of the 10 stacking sequences are compatible with the ($n+2 =$) 10-ply results and; only 20 of the 31 stacking sequences are compatible with the 8-ply results. The 10-ply stacking sequences are however all compatible with the ($n+2 =$) 12-ply results, as are those between 12- and 14 plies. Full compatibility was seen throughout the earlier result, hence the reason for omitting the $n+2$ results in parentheses from Column (5) of Tables 1 - 6. This compatibility is however further disrupted in the transition between the *Extension-Shearing Bending-Twisting* coupled laminate results and the *Simple* laminate results. Column (8) suggests that this is due to the changing pattern of ply terminations across the transition.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This article has investigated the extent of the design space for tapered warp-free laminates, with both uncoupled and mechanically coupled properties, when a two ply termination scheme is applied and ply contiguity (≤ 2) is accounted. A number of key conclusions can be drawn from the results presented:

Balanced angle-ply terminations are permissible in *Simple* and *Bending-Twisting* coupled laminate configurations with odd ply number groupings; only cross-ply termination are permissible in even ply number groupings. Such restrictions are not seen in *Extension-Shearing Bending-Twisting* coupled laminates.

Lamination parameter point clouds can reveal strings of points representing the tapered designs found. These graphical representations of the design space offer insight into the potential for tailoring of stiffness properties through ply terminations.

The transition between *Extension-Shearing Bending-Twisting* coupled laminates and *Simple* laminates has been demonstrated through a two ply termination scheme.

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